

Liver PPI

Compare Outcomes Analysis

Introduction

TriNetX is the global federated health research network providing access to electronic medical records (diagnoses, procedures, medications, laboratory values, genomic information) across large healthcare organizations (HCOs). This report was run on the set of HCOs grouped into a network called Research. This network included 76 HCO(s).

This report describes a Compare Outcomes Analysis, named NASH Outcomes balance lab/med 1.13.23, generated by the TriNetX platform on Jan 13, 2023, 18:39:51 UTC. This analysis compared the outcomes of two cohorts: Cohort A (3,003 patients) named NASH PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23 and Cohort B (3,807 patients) named NASH No PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23.

Methods

The analysis process includes two main steps: 1) Defining the cohorts through query criteria; 2) Setting up and running the analysis. Setting up the analysis requires definitions for the index event, outcomes criteria, and the time frame. Compare outcomes supports four analyses: Measures of Association, Survival, Number of Instances and Lab result distribution. These analyses have additional options that are listed in the Outcomes Definitions and Analyses Specifications section below. Furthermore, characteristics of the cohorts that are balanced using propensity score matching are also included in the Propensity Score Matching section.

Cohorts definition

This section lists all terms used in the definitions of the two cohorts.

Query Criteria for Cohort 1 (query name: NASH PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23)

This query was run on the network Research with 76 HCO(s) queried and 76 HCO(s) responded. A total of 49 provider(s) responded with patients. The final cohort included 3,003 patients who matched the query criteria listed in the table below. For the text representation of the query criteria please see Appendix A.

Ungrouped terms				
must have	demographics	Age	Age (at least 18 years (most recent occurrence))	
cannot have	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:E83.01	Wilson's disease	
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:E88.01	Alpha-1-antitrypsin deficiency
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K83.0	Cholangitis
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K74.3	Primary biliary cirrhosis
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K75.4	Autoimmune hepatitis
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:B15-B19	Viral hepatitis
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K70.3	Alcoholic cirrhosis of liver
Group 1				
Group 1A NASH and cirrhosis				
must have	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K74.60	Unspecified cirrhosis of liver	
	and	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K75.81	Nonalcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH)
date constraint	The terms in this group occurred between Apr 1, 2003 and Jan 1, 2019			
event relationship	Any instance of PPI occurred within 3 months before or up to 3 years after any instance of NASH and cirrhosis			

Group 1B PPI				
must have	any of	medication	NLM:RXNORM:816346	dexlansoprazole
		medication	NLM:RXNORM:283742	esomeprazole
		medication	NLM:RXNORM:17128	lansoprazole
		medication	NLM:RXNORM:40790	pantoprazole
		medication	NLM:RXNORM:7646	Omeprazole

Group 2

Group 2A NASH and cirrhosis				
must have		diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K74.60	Unspecified cirrhosis of liver
	and	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K75.81	Nonalcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH)
date constraint		The terms in this group occurred between Apr 1, 2003 and Jan 1, 2019		
event relationship		Any instance of No Liver decompensation events occurred on or before any instance of NASH and cirrhosis		

Group 2B No Liver decompensation events				
cannot have		diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K65.2	Spontaneous bacterial peritonitis
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:A41	Other sepsis
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:C22.0	Liver cell carcinoma
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K72	Hepatic failure, not elsewhere classified
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:I85	Esophageal varices
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K76.7	Hepatorenal syndrome
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:R18	Ascites

Query Criteria for Cohort 2 (query name: NASH No PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23)

This query was run on the network Research with 76 HCO(s) queried and 76 HCO(s) responded. A total of 54 provider(s) responded with patients. The final cohort included 3,807 patients who matched the query criteria listed in the table below.

Ungrouped terms				
must have		demographics	Age	Age (at least 18 years (most recent occurrence))
cannot have		diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:E83.01	Wilson's disease
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:E88.01	Alpha-1-antitrypsin deficiency
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K83.0	Cholangitis
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K74.3	Primary biliary cirrhosis
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K75.4	Autoimmune hepatitis
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:B15-B19	Viral hepatitis
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K70.3	Alcoholic cirrhosis of liver

Group 1

Group 1A NASH and cirrhosis				
must have		diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K74.60	Unspecified cirrhosis of liver
	and	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K75.81	Nonalcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH)
date constraint		The terms in this group occurred between Apr 1, 2003 and Jan 1, 2019		
event relationship		Any instance of No PPI occurred within 3 months before or up to 3 years after any instance of NASH and cirrhosis		

Group 1B No PPI				
cannot have		medication	NLM:RXNORM:816346	dexlansoprazole
	or	medication	NLM:RXNORM:283742	esomeprazole
	or	medication	NLM:RXNORM:17128	lansoprazole
	or	medication	NLM:RXNORM:40790	pantoprazole
	or	medication	NLM:RXNORM:7646	Omeprazole

Group 2

Group 2A NASH and cirrhosis				
must have		diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K74.60	Unspecified cirrhosis of liver
	and	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K75.81	Nonalcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH)
date constraint		The terms in this group occurred between Apr 1, 2003 and Jan 1, 2019		

event relationship	Any instance of excluding Liver decompensation events occurred on or before any instance of NASH and cirrhosis		
Group 2B excluding Liver decompensation events			
cannot have	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K65.2	Spontaneous bacterial peritonitis
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:A41
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:C22.0
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K72
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:I85
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K76.7
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:R18
			Ascites

Analysis Setup

This section contains the Index Event and Time Window definitions and a list of selected outcomes and the analyses.

Index Event & Time Window Definitions

The index event defines the point in time when each patient in the cohort enters the analysis. To define an index event for the cohort, one or more criteria for the cohort must be selected. The index date for each patient within a cohort is the day on which the patient first met the selected criteria for the cohort (listed in the table below).

As the index event defines the earliest time point after which outcomes are analyzed, the time window defines the duration during which outcomes are analyzed. The time window can start on the same day as the index event or at any specified time interval after the index event. The time window can end any time after the start date. Outcomes are defined as diagnoses, medications, procedures, or laboratory values that happened in the time window starting after the first occurrence of the index event.

Time Window Used in this Analysis

This analysis included outcomes that occurred in the time window that started on the same day as the first occurrence of the index event and ended 1095 days after the first occurrence of the index event

The index event only includes events that occurred up to 20 years ago. Patients whose index event occurred 20 years or more ago are excluded. In this analysis, 0 patients in Cohort 1 and 0 patients in Cohort 2 were excluded because they met the index event more than 20 years ago.

Index Events Used in this Analysis

Index events for the Compare Outcomes analysis were derived from the cohort definitions. Index events were defined separately for each cohort and were based on the criteria used in the original cohort definition. Please see Appendix B for the text representation of the index event definition.

The index event for Cohort 1 (query name: NASH PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23) was defined as the following:

Group 1				
Group 1A NASH and cirrhosis				
must have		diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K74.60	Unspecified cirrhosis of liver
	and	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K75.81	Nonalcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH)
date constraint	The terms in this group occurred between Apr 1, 2003 and Jan 1, 2019			
event relationship	Any instance of PPI occurred within 3 months before or up to 3 years after any instance of NASH and cirrhosis			
Group 1B PPI				
must have	any of	medication	NLM:RXNORM:816346	dexlansoprazole

medication	NLM:RXNORM:283742	esomeprazole
medication	NLM:RXNORM:17128	lansoprazole
medication	NLM:RXNORM:40790	pantoprazole
medication	NLM:RXNORM:7646	Omeprazole

The index event for Cohort 2 (query name: NASH No PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23) was defined as the following:

Group 1			
Group 1A NASH and cirrhosis			
must have	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K74.60	Unspecified cirrhosis of liver
	and	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K75.81
date constraint	The terms in this group occurred between Apr 1, 2003 and Jan 1, 2019		
event relationship	Any instance of No PPI occurred within 3 months before or up to 3 years after any instance of NASH and cirrhosis		
Group 1B No PPI			
cannot have	medication	NLM:RXNORM:816346	dexlansoprazole
	or	medication	NLM:RXNORM:283742
	or	medication	NLM:RXNORM:17128
	or	medication	NLM:RXNORM:40790
	or	medication	NLM:RXNORM:7646

Analyses Specifications

The Compare Outcomes Analytic supports four types of analyses: Measure of Association, Survival, Number of Instances, and Lab result distribution. The first three analyses support the “exclude patients with outcomes prior to the window” setting. This option can exclude patients from the analysis if they are not at risk for an outcome (e.g., if the outcome is a chronic disease). When "exclude patients with the outcome prior to the time window" is not checked, all patients in the cohort are included in the analysis, regardless of whether they had the outcome prior to the time window. When "exclude patients with the outcome prior to the time window" is checked, patients are excluded from the analysis if their record includes the outcome prior to the beginning of the time window. This selection will exclude all patients with the outcome prior to the index event. If the start of the time window for the analysis falls some days after the index event, patients will also be excluded if they have the outcome between the index event and the start of the time window.

Measure of Association Analysis

The Measure of Association Analysis calculates and compares the fraction of patients with the selected outcome. The output summary includes: Patients in each Cohort (count of patients meeting query criteria); Patients with Outcome in each Cohort (of the patients in the cohort, count of patients that had the outcome in the time window); and Risk (the fraction of patients in the cohort that have the outcome in the time window, i.e. Patients with Outcome / Patients in Cohort). In addition, Risk Difference (the difference in the risks in Cohort 1 and Cohort 2), Risk Ratio (the ratio of the risks in Cohort 1 and Cohort 2), and Odds Ratio (the ratio of the odds in Cohort 1 and Cohort 2). The bar chart shows the risk of the outcome for the both cohorts.

Survival Analysis

The Kaplan-Meier Analysis estimates probability of the outcome at a respective time interval (daily time interval is used in this analysis). In order to account for the patients who exited the cohort during the analysis period, and therefore should not be included in the analysis, censoring is applied. In this analysis, patients are removed from the analysis (censored) after the last fact in their record.

The output summary includes: Patients in each Cohort (count of patients meeting query criteria); Patients with Outcome (of the patients in the cohort, count of patients that had the outcome in the time window); Median Survival (the number of days when the survival drops below 50%; the “-” indicates that survival does not drop below 50% during the time window); and Survival Probability at End of Time Window (the % survival at the end of the time window). In addition, Log-Rank test, Hazard Ratio and test for Proportionality.

Number of Instances Analysis

The Number of Instances Analysis calculates how many times the outcome occurred in the time window. This analysis includes two additional settings: include patients with zero instances; the definition of an instance.

Selecting to exclude patients with zero instances will remove these patients from the calculations for mean number of instances, standard deviation, or median. The histogram showing the distribution of patients by number of instances will not contain a bar for zero. Alternatively, by selecting to include patients with zero instances, the mean, standard deviation, and median for number of instances will reflect these patients. The histogram will contain a bar for zero patients.

The definition of an instance affects how counts are analyzed. By selecting Date, each calendar date on which any of the terms selected in the outcome are recorded will represent one instance. For example, if the outcome is “Med A or Med B,” and a patient has “Med A” on January 3, then both medications on January 4, then “Med B” on January 6, then that patient is considered to have three instances— January 3, January 4, and January 6. Note that if an outcome occurs across several dates (e.g. Visit: inpatient encounter), then only the start date is tracked for the purpose of counting instances. A patient who begins at stay on January 1, ends that stay on January 3, begins another stay on January 10, and ends that stay on January 15, is considered to have two instances of the outcome.

Selecting Visit as an Instance will count any visit that includes the outcome as one instance, regardless of how many times it occurred. For instance, consider a patient administered an analgesic on each of the three days that make up an inpatient stay following some index event. If analgesic is an outcome, these three administrations will represent only one instance, because all three are associated with the same visit.

The output summary includes: Patients in Cohort (count of patients meeting query criteria); Patients with Outcome (of the patients in the cohort, count of patients that had the outcome in the time window); Mean (mean of the counts); Standard Deviation (standard deviation of the counts); Median (median of the counts); and Median (1+ instances) when patients with zero instances included in the analysis. In addition, T-Test statistics testing for the difference between the cohorts is included.

Laboratory Results Analysis

Lab Results can be included in the analysis only for the outcomes that are labs. Only the most recent lab values in the time window are included. For the lab results that are numeric, the outcome summary includes: Patients in Cohort (count of patients meeting query criteria); Patients with Outcome (of the patients in the cohort, count of patients that had the outcome in the time window); Mean (mean of the counts); and Standard Deviation (the standard deviation for lab values across patients in the cohort). In addition, T-Test statistics testing for the difference between the cohorts is included.

For the non-numeric lab results, three values are reported: counts of Negative; Positives; and Unknowns. The counts are represented in the bar chart as percentages of the total counts.

Outcome Definitions

Table below outlines the definitions for each outcome and the analysis specifications. For outcome definitions consisting of more than one term, at least one term must match. Please see Appendix C for the text representation of the outcome definitions.

Ascites		
Outcome definition		
Diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:R18	Ascites
Settings for the performed analyses		
Risk analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Kaplan - Meier survival analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Esophageal varices I85		
Outcome definition		
Diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:I85	Esophageal varices
Settings for the performed analyses		
Risk analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Kaplan - Meier survival analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Esophageal varices w/o bleeding I85.0		
Outcome definition		
Diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:I85.00	Esophageal varices without bleeding
Settings for the performed analyses		
Risk analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Kaplan - Meier survival analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Esophageal varices w/ bleeding I85.01		
Outcome definition		
Diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:I85.01	Esophageal varices with bleeding
Settings for the performed analyses		
Risk analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Kaplan - Meier survival analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Hepatic failure, not elsewhere specified K72		
Outcome definition		
Diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K72	Hepatic failure, not elsewhere classified
Settings for the performed analyses		
Risk analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Kaplan - Meier survival analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Hepatic failure, unspecified K72.9		
Outcome definition		
Diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K72.9	Hepatic failure, unspecified
Settings for the performed analyses		
Risk analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Kaplan - Meier survival analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Hepatorenal syndrome K76.7		
Outcome definition		
Diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K76.7	Hepatorenal syndrome
Settings for the performed analyses		
Risk analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Kaplan - Meier survival analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Liver cell carcinoma C22.0		
Outcome definition		
Diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:C22.0	Liver cell carcinoma
Settings for the performed analyses		
Risk analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Kaplan - Meier survival analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Sepsis A41		
Outcome definition		

Diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:A41	Other sepsis
Settings for the performed analyses		
Risk analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Kaplan - Meier survival analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Sepsis Enterococcus A41.81		
Outcome definition		
Diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:A41.81	Sepsis due to Enterococcus
Settings for the performed analyses		
Risk analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Kaplan - Meier survival analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Spontaneous bacterial peritonitis K65.2		
Outcome definition		
Diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K65.2	Spontaneous bacterial peritonitis
Settings for the performed analyses		
Risk analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Kaplan - Meier survival analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Mortality		
Outcome definition		
Demographics	Deceased	Deceased
Settings for the performed analyses		
Risk analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Kaplan - Meier survival analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window

Propensity Score Matching

Propensity score matching was performed on all listed characteristics. Characteristics of the cohorts before and after matching are summarized in the table below.

Cohort 1 and cohort 2 patient count before and after propensity score matching		
Cohort	Patient count before matching	Patient count after matching
1 - NASH PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	3,003	2,307
2 - NASH No PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	3,807	2,307

Cohort 1 (N = 3,003) and cohort 2 (N = 3,807) characteristics before propensity score matching							
Demographics							
Cohort			Mean \pm SD	Patients	% of Cohort	P-Value	Std diff.
1	AI	Age at Index	60.0 \pm 12.8	3,003	100%	0.001	0.079
2			59.0 \pm 13.3	3,807	100%		
1	M	Male		959	31.9%	0.001	0.079
2			1,358	35.7%			

Diagnosis							
Cohort			Mean \pm SD	Patients	% of Cohort	P-Value	Std diff.
1	I21	Acute myocardial infarction		162	5.4%	<0.001	0.171
2				82	2.2%		
1	I50	Heart failure		474	15.8%	<0.001	0.215
2				334	8.8%		
1	I73	Other peripheral vascular diseases		223	7.4%	<0.001	0.159
2				144	3.8%		
1	I63.5	Cerebral infarction due to unspecified occlusion or stenosis of cerebral arteries		53	1.8%	0.006	0.066
2				38	1.0%		
1	J44	Other chronic obstructive pulmonary disease		400	13.3%	<0.001	0.222
2				255	6.7%		
1	N18	Chronic kidney disease (CKD)		519	17.3%	<0.001	0.175
2				426	11.2%		
1	C81-C96	Malignant neoplasms of lymphoid, hematopoietic and related tissue		71	2.4%	0.001	0.078
2				50	1.3%		
1	I25	Chronic ischemic heart disease		726	24.2%	<0.001	0.286
2				500	13.1%		
1	E11	Type 2 diabetes mellitus		1,796	59.8%	<0.001	0.233
2				1,837	48.3%		
1	C00-C14	Malignant neoplasms of lip, oral cavity and pharynx		11	0.4%	0.576	0.014
2				11	0.3%		
1	C15-C26	Malignant neoplasms of digestive organs		156	5.2%	<0.001	0.110
2				115	3.0%		
1	C30-C39	Malignant neoplasms of respiratory and intrathoracic organs		42	1.4%	0.001	0.080
2				23	0.6%		
1	C40-C41	Malignant neoplasms of bone and articular cartilage		10	0.3%	0.594	0.013
2				10	0.3%		
1	C43-C44	Melanoma and other malignant neoplasms of skin		102	3.4%	0.085	0.042
2				102	2.7%		
1	C45-C49	Malignant neoplasms of mesothelial and soft tissue		14	0.5%	0.159	0.034
2				10	0.3%		
1	C50-C50	Malignant neoplasms of breast (C50)		116	3.9%	0.178	0.033
2				124	3.3%		
1	C51-C58	Malignant neoplasms of female genital organs		70	2.3%	0.096	0.040
2				67	1.8%		
1	C60-C63	Malignant neoplasms of male genital organs		45	1.5%	0.021	0.056
2				34	0.9%		
1	C64-C68	Malignant neoplasms of urinary tract		46	1.5%	0.341	0.023
2				48	1.3%		
1	C69-C72	Malignant neoplasms of eye, brain and other parts of central nervous system		10	0.3%	0.594	0.013
2				10	0.3%		
1	C73-C75	Malignant neoplasms of thyroid and other endocrine glands		19	0.6%	0.560	0.014
2				20	0.5%		

1	C76-C80	Malignant neoplasms of ill-defined, other secondary and unspecified sites	134	4.5%	0.008	0.064
2			123	3.2%		
1	C7A-C7A	Malignant neuroendocrine tumors (C7A)	13	0.4%	0.425	0.019
2			12	0.3%		
1	C7B-C7B	Secondary neuroendocrine tumors (C7B)	10	0.3%	0.594	0.013
2			10	0.3%		

Medication							
Cohort			Mean ± SD	Patients	% of Cohort	P-Value	Std diff.
1	4603	furosemide		1,019	33.9%	<0.001	0.489
2			522	13.7%			
1	9997	spironolactone		532	17.7%	<0.001	0.310
2			287	7.5%			
1	6218	lactulose		440	14.7%	<0.001	0.349
2			172	4.5%			
1	35619	rifaximin		251	8.4%	<0.001	0.259
2			96	2.5%			
1	8787	propranolol		167	5.6%	<0.001	0.173
2			85	2.2%			
1	7226	nadolol		136	4.5%	<0.001	0.136
2			80	2.1%			
1	20352	carvedilol		287	9.6%	<0.001	0.214
2			159	4.2%			

Laboratory							
Cohort			Mean ± SD	Patients	% of Cohort	P-Value	Std diff.
1	9050	Bilirubin.total [Mass/volume] in Serum, Plasma or Blood	1.1 +/- 1.9	2,522	84.0%	<0.001	0.107
2			0.9 +/- 1.0	2,456	64.5%		
1		1.30 - 0 mg/dL		753	25.1%	<0.001	0.213
2			627	16.5%			
1	9045	Albumin [Mass/volume] in Serum, Plasma or Blood	3.7 +/- 0.7	2,198	73.2%	<0.001	0.189
2			3.9 +/- 0.6	2,249	59.1%		
1		0 - 3.50 g/dL		1,361	45.3%	<0.001	0.426
2			967	25.4%			
1	9032	INR in Plasma or Blood	1.2 +/- 0.5	2,187	72.8%	<0.001	0.175
2			1.2 +/- 0.3	2,036	53.5%		
1		1.20 - 0 {INR}		1,010	33.6%	<0.001	0.318
2			752	19.8%			

Cohort 1 (N = 2,307) and cohort 2 (N = 2,307) characteristics after propensity score matching

Demographics							
Cohort			Mean ± SD	Patients	% of Cohort	P-Value	Std diff.
1	AI	Age at Index	59.3 +/- 13.0	2,307	100%	0.352	0.027
2			59.0 +/- 13.4	2,307	100%		
1	M	Male		741	32.1%	0.615	0.015
2			757	32.8%			

Diagnosis							
Cohort			Mean ± SD	Patients	% of Cohort	P-Value	Std diff.
1	I21	Acute myocardial infarction		86	3.7%	0.473	0.021
2			77	3.3%			

1	I50	Heart failure	259	11.2%	0.781	0.008
2			265	11.5%		
1	I73	Other peripheral vascular diseases	114	4.9%	0.465	0.022
2			125	5.4%		
1	I63.5	Cerebral infarction due to unspecified occlusion or stenosis of cerebral arteries	34	1.5%	0.804	0.007
2			32	1.4%		
1	J44	Other chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	212	9.2%	0.546	0.018
2			224	9.7%		
1	N18	Chronic kidney disease (CKD)	325	14.1%	0.966	0.001
2			324	14.0%		
1	C81-C96	Malignant neoplasms of lymphoid, hematopoietic and related tissue	48	2.1%	0.597	0.016
2			43	1.9%		
1	I25	Chronic ischemic heart disease	432	18.7%	0.851	0.006
2			437	18.9%		
1	E11	Type 2 diabetes mellitus	1,302	56.4%	0.405	0.025
2			1,330	57.7%		
1	C00-C14	Malignant neoplasms of lip, oral cavity and pharynx	10	0.4%	1	<0.001
2			10	0.4%		
1	C15-C26	Malignant neoplasms of digestive organs	91	3.9%	0.461	0.022
2			101	4.4%		
1	C30-C39	Malignant neoplasms of respiratory and intrathoracic organs	22	1.0%	0.881	0.004
2			23	1.0%		
1	C40-C41	Malignant neoplasms of bone and articular cartilage	10	0.4%	1	<0.001
2			10	0.4%		
1	C43-C44	Melanoma and other malignant neoplasms of skin	75	3.3%	0.869	0.005
2			77	3.3%		
1	C45-C49	Malignant neoplasms of mesothelial and soft tissue	10	0.4%	1	<0.001
2			10	0.4%		
1	C50-C50	Malignant neoplasms of breast (C50)	85	3.7%	0.813	0.007
2			82	3.6%		
1	C51-C58	Malignant neoplasms of female genital organs	50	2.2%	0.680	0.012
2			46	2.0%		
1	C60-C63	Malignant neoplasms of male genital organs	29	1.3%	0.894	0.004
2			28	1.2%		
1	C64-C68	Malignant neoplasms of urinary tract	34	1.5%	0.810	0.007
2			36	1.6%		
1	C69-C72	Malignant neoplasms of eye, brain and other parts of central nervous system	10	0.4%	1	<0.001
2			10	0.4%		
1	C73-C75	Malignant neoplasms of thyroid and other endocrine glands	12	0.5%	0.841	0.006
2			13	0.6%		
1	C76-C80	Malignant neoplasms of ill-defined, other secondary and unspecified sites	89	3.9%	0.599	0.015
2			96	4.2%		
1	C7A-C7A	Malignant neuroendocrine tumors (C7A)	10	0.4%	1	<0.001
2			10	0.4%		

1	C7B-C7B	Secondary neuroendocrine tumors (C7B)	10	0.4%	1	<0.001	
2			10	0.4%			
Medication							
Cohort			Mean ± SD	Patients	% of Cohort	P-Value	Std diff.
1	4603	furosemide		517	22.4%	0.860	0.005
2			512	22.2%			
1	9997	spironolactone		270	11.7%	0.927	0.003
2			268	11.6%			
1	6218	lactulose		187	8.1%	0.349	0.028
2			170	7.4%			
1	35619	rifaximin		106	4.6%	0.309	0.030
2			92	4.0%			
1	8787	propranolol		88	3.8%	0.756	0.009
2			84	3.6%			
1	7226	nadolol		83	3.6%	0.517	0.019
2			75	3.3%			
1	20352	carvedilol		163	7.1%	0.288	0.031
2			145	6.3%			
Laboratory							
Cohort			Mean ± SD	Patients	% of Cohort	P-Value	Std diff.
1	9050	Bilirubin.total [Mass/volume] in Serum, Plasma or Blood	0.9 +/- 1.4	1,894	82.1%	0.599	0.018
2			0.9 +/- 1.0	1,657	71.8%		
1		1.30 - 0 mg/dL		480	20.8%	0.772	0.009
2			488	21.2%			
1	9045	Albumin [Mass/volume] in Serum, Plasma or Blood	3.9 +/- 0.6	1,620	70.2%	<0.001	0.200
2			3.7 +/- 0.6	1,512	65.5%		
1		0 - 3.50 g/dL		839	36.4%	0.212	0.037
2			880	38.1%			
1	9032	INR in Plasma or Blood	1.2 +/- 0.4	1,616	70.0%	0.733	0.013
2			1.2 +/- 0.3	1,393	60.4%		
1		1.20 - 0 {INR}		628	27.2%	0.715	0.011
2			617	26.7%			

Results

Results are summarized in the table below. Analysis was performed on the cohorts after propensity score matching.

1 Ascites

Risk analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Risk	
1 NASH PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	230	0.100	
2 NASH No PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	179	0.078	
		95% CI	z	p
Risk Difference	0.022	(0.006, 0.038)	2.642	0.008
Risk Ratio	1.285	(1.066, 1.549)	N/A	N/A
Odds Ratio	1.316	(1.073, 1.615)	N/A	N/A

Kaplan - Meier survival analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Median survival (days)	Survival probability at end of time window	
1 NASH PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	230	--	88.30%	
2 NASH No PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	179	--	90.60%	
	χ^2	df	p		
Log-Rank Test	4.815	1	0.028		
	Hazard Ratio	95% CI	χ^2	df	p
Hazard Ratio and Proportionality	1.243	(1.023, 1.512)	0.288	1	0.591

2 Esophageal varices I85

Risk analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Risk	
1 NASH PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	254	0.110	
2 NASH No PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	177	0.077	
		95% CI	z	p
Risk Difference	0.033	(0.017, 0.050)	3.895	0.000
Risk Ratio	1.435	(1.195, 1.723)	N/A	N/A
Odds Ratio	1.489	(1.217, 1.821)	N/A	N/A

Kaplan - Meier survival analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Median survival (days)	Survival probability at end of time window	
1 NASH PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	254	--	87.11%	
2 NASH No PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	177	--	90.40%	
	χ^2	df	p		
Log-Rank Test	12.497	1	0.000		
	Hazard Ratio	95% CI	χ^2	df	p
Hazard Ratio and Proportionality	1.411	(1.165, 1.710)	3.976	1	0.046

3 Esophageal varices w/o bleeding I85.0

Risk analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Risk
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1	NASH PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	188	0.081	
2	NASH No PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	119	0.052	
			95% CI	z	p
Risk Difference		0.030	(0.016, 0.044)	4.076	0.000
Risk Ratio		1.580	(1.265, 1.973)	N/A	N/A
Odds Ratio		1.631	(1.287, 2.068)	N/A	N/A

Kaplan - Meier survival analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Median survival (days)	Survival probability at end of time window		
1 NASH PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	188	--	90.34%		
2 NASH No PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	119	--	93.41%		
Log-Rank Test		χ^2 14.029	df 1	p 0.000		
Hazard Ratio and Proportionality		Hazard Ratio 1.546	95% CI (1.228, 1.944)	χ^2 3.922	df 1	p 0.048

4 Esophageal varices w/ bleeding I85.01

Risk analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Risk
1 NASH PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	19	0.008
2 NASH No PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	10	0.004

		95% CI	z	p
Risk Difference	0.004	(-0.001, 0.008)	1.677	0.094
Risk Ratio	1.900	(0.885, 4.077)	N/A	N/A
Odds Ratio	1.907	(0.885, 4.111)	N/A	N/A

Kaplan - Meier survival analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Median survival (days)	Survival probability at end of time window
1 NASH PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	19	--	99.04%
2 NASH No PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	10	--	99.51%

	χ^2	df	p
Log-Rank Test	3.232	1	0.072

	Hazard Ratio	95% CI	χ^2	df	p
Hazard Ratio and Proportionality	2.039	(0.922, 4.506)	0.768	1	0.381

5 Hepatic failure, not elsewhere specified K72

Risk analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Risk
1 NASH PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	176	0.076
2 NASH No PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	129	0.056

		95% CI	z	p
Risk Difference	0.020	(0.006, 0.035)	2.785	0.005
Risk Ratio	1.364	(1.095, 1.700)	N/A	N/A
Odds Ratio	1.394	(1.103, 1.764)	N/A	N/A

Kaplan - Meier survival analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Median survival (days)	Survival probability at end of time window
1 NASH PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	176	--	91.17%
2 NASH No PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	129	--	93.18%

	χ^2	df	p
Log-Rank Test	5.867	1	0.015

	Hazard Ratio	95% CI	χ^2	df	p
Hazard Ratio and Proportionality	1.323	(1.054, 1.660)	0.536	1	0.464

6 Hepatic failure, unspecified K72.9

Risk analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Risk
1 NASH PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	159	0.069
2 NASH No PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	122	0.053

		95% CI	z	p
Risk Difference	0.016	(0.002, 0.030)	2.278	0.023
Risk Ratio	1.303	(1.037, 1.638)	N/A	N/A
Odds Ratio	1.326	(1.039, 1.691)	N/A	N/A

Kaplan - Meier survival analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Median survival (days)	Survival probability at end of time window
1 NASH PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	159	--	92.01%
2 NASH No PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	122	--	93.52%

Log-Rank Test	χ^2	df	p
	3.762	1	0.052

Hazard Ratio and Proportionality	Hazard Ratio	95% CI	χ^2	df	p
	1.262	(0.997, 1.598)	1.045	1	0.307

7 Hepatorenal syndrome K76.7

Risk analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Risk
1 NASH PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	19	0.008
2 NASH No PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	11	0.005

	95% CI	z	p
Risk Difference	(-0.001, 0.008)	1.465	0.143
Risk Ratio	(0.824, 3.621)	N/A	N/A
Odds Ratio	(0.823, 3.651)	N/A	N/A

Kaplan - Meier survival analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Median survival (days)	Survival probability at end of time window		
1 NASH PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	19	--	99.08%		
2 NASH No PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	11	--	99.40%		
		χ^2	df	p		
Log-Rank Test		1.881	1	0.170		
		Hazard Ratio	95% CI	χ^2	df	p
Hazard Ratio and Proportionality		1.672	(0.796, 3.513)	2.853	1	0.091

8 Liver cell carcinoma C22.0

Risk analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Risk		
1 NASH PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	107	0.046		
2 NASH No PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	84	0.036		
		95% CI	z	p	
Risk Difference		0.010	(-0.002, 0.021)	1.700	0.089
Risk Ratio		1.274	(0.963, 1.685)	N/A	N/A
Odds Ratio		1.287	(0.961, 1.723)	N/A	N/A

Kaplan - Meier survival analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Median survival (days)	Survival probability at end of time window
1 NASH PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	107	--	94.39%
2 NASH No PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	84	--	95.51%

	χ^2	df	p
Log-Rank Test	2.015	1	0.156

	Hazard Ratio	95% CI	χ^2	df	p
Hazard Ratio and Proportionality	1.229	(0.924, 1.636)	0.430	1	0.512

9 Sepsis A41

Risk analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Risk
1 NASH PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	133	0.058
2 NASH No PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	89	0.039

		95% CI	z	p
Risk Difference	0.019	(0.007, 0.031)	3.027	0.002
Risk Ratio	1.494	(1.150, 1.942)	N/A	N/A
Odds Ratio	1.525	(1.158, 2.007)	N/A	N/A

Kaplan - Meier survival analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Median survival (days)	Survival probability at end of time window
1 NASH PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	133	--	93.24%
2 NASH No PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	89	--	95.13%

	χ^2	df	p
Log-Rank Test	7.330	1	0.007

	Hazard Ratio	95% CI	χ^2	df	p
Hazard Ratio and Proportionality	1.446	(1.105, 1.891)	2.034	1	0.154

10 Sepsis Enterococcus A41.81

Risk analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Risk
1 NASH PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	10	0.004
2 NASH No PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	10	0.004

	95% CI	z	p
Risk Difference	0 (-0.004, 0.004)	0	1
Risk Ratio	1 (0.417, 2.398)	N/A	N/A
Odds Ratio	1 (0.415, 2.407)	N/A	N/A

Kaplan - Meier survival analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Median survival (days)	Survival probability at end of time window	
1 NASH PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	10	--	99.96%	
2 NASH No PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	10	--	99.90%	
Log-Rank Test		χ^2 0.361	df 1	p 0.548	
Hazard Ratio and Proportionality		Hazard Ratio 0.487	95% CI (0.044, 5.368)	χ^2 2.255	df 1
				p 0.133	

11 Spontaneous bacterial peritonitis K65.2

Risk analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Risk		
1 NASH PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	20	0.009		
2 NASH No PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	11	0.005		
Risk Difference		0.004	95% CI (-0.001, 0.009)	z 1.622	p 0.105
Risk Ratio		1.818	(0.873, 3.786)	N/A	N/A
Odds Ratio		1.825	(0.873, 3.818)	N/A	N/A

Kaplan - Meier survival analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Median survival (days)	Survival probability at end of time window		
1 NASH PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	20	--	99.02%		
2 NASH No PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	11	--	99.44%		
		χ^2	df	p		
Log-Rank Test	2.361	1	0.124			
		Hazard Ratio	95% CI	χ^2	df	p
Hazard Ratio and Proportionality	1.766	(0.846, 3.687)	0.217	1	0.641	

12 Mortality

Risk analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Risk		
1 NASH PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	241	0.104		
2 NASH No PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	249	0.108		
		95% CI	z	p	
Risk Difference	-0.003	(-0.021, 0.014)	-0.382	0.702	
Risk Ratio	0.968	(0.819, 1.144)	N/A	N/A	
Odds Ratio	0.964	(0.799, 1.163)	N/A	N/A	

Kaplan - Meier survival analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Median survival (days)	Survival probability at end of time window
1 NASH PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	241	--	87.87%
2 NASH No PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	2,307	249	--	86.86%

	χ^2	df	p
Log-Rank Test	0.746	1	0.388

	Hazard Ratio	95% CI	χ^2	df	p
Hazard Ratio and Proportionality	0.925	(0.775, 1.104)	0.172	1	0.678

Appendix A – Text Representation of the Cohorts Definition

This section lists all terms used in the definitions of the two cohorts.

Query Criteria for Cohort 1 (query name: NASH PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23)

Patients must have:

Age (Age) (at least 18 years (most recent occurrence)).

Patients cannot have:

any of the following:

Wilson's disease (UMLS:ICD10CM:E83.01); or
Alpha-1-antitrypsin deficiency (UMLS:ICD10CM:E88.01); or
Cholangitis (UMLS:ICD10CM:K83.0); or
Primary biliary cirrhosis (UMLS:ICD10CM:K74.3); or
Autoimmune hepatitis (UMLS:ICD10CM:K75.4); or
Viral hepatitis (UMLS:ICD10CM:B15-B19); or
Alcoholic cirrhosis of liver (UMLS:ICD10CM:K70.3).

All the following must be satisfied:

NASH and cirrhosis: The terms in this group occurred between Apr 1, 2003 and Jan 1, 2019

Patients must have:

all of the following:

Unspecified cirrhosis of liver (UMLS:ICD10CM:K74.60); and
Nonalcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH) (UMLS:ICD10CM:K75.81).

PPI: Any instance of PPI occurred within 3 months before or up to 3 years after any instance of NASH and cirrhosis

Patients must have:

any of the following:

dexlansoprazole (NLM:RXNORM:816346); or
esomeprazole (NLM:RXNORM:283742); or
lansoprazole (NLM:RXNORM:17128); or
pantoprazole (NLM:RXNORM:40790); or
Omeprazole (NLM:RXNORM:7646).

NASH and cirrhosis: The terms in this group occurred between Apr 1, 2003 and Jan 1, 2019

Patients must have:

all of the following:

Unspecified cirrhosis of liver (UMLS:ICD10CM:K74.60); and
Nonalcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH) (UMLS:ICD10CM:K75.81).

No Liver decompensation events: Any instance of No Liver decompensation events occurred on or before any instance of NASH and cirrhosis

Patients cannot have:

any of the following:

Spontaneous bacterial peritonitis (UMLS:ICD10CM:K65.2); or
Other sepsis (UMLS:ICD10CM:A41); or

Liver cell carcinoma (UMLS:ICD10CM:C22.0); or
Hepatic failure, not elsewhere classified (UMLS:ICD10CM:K72); or
Esophageal varices (UMLS:ICD10CM:I85); or
Hepatorenal syndrome (UMLS:ICD10CM:K76.7); or
Ascites (UMLS:ICD10CM:R18).

Query Criteria for Cohort 2 (query name: NASH No PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23)

Patients must have:

Age (Age) (at least 18 years (most recent occurrence)).

Patients cannot have:

any of the following:

Wilson's disease (UMLS:ICD10CM:E83.01); or
Alpha-1-antitrypsin deficiency (UMLS:ICD10CM:E88.01); or
Cholangitis (UMLS:ICD10CM:K83.0); or
Primary biliary cirrhosis (UMLS:ICD10CM:K74.3); or
Autoimmune hepatitis (UMLS:ICD10CM:K75.4); or
Viral hepatitis (UMLS:ICD10CM:B15-B19); or
Alcoholic cirrhosis of liver (UMLS:ICD10CM:K70.3).

All the following must be satisfied:

NASH and cirrhosis: The terms in this group occurred between Apr 1, 2003 and Jan 1, 2019

Patients must have:

all of the following:

Unspecified cirrhosis of liver (UMLS:ICD10CM:K74.60); and
Nonalcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH) (UMLS:ICD10CM:K75.81).

No PPI: Any instance of No PPI occurred within 3 months before or up to 3 years after any instance of NASH and cirrhosis

Patients cannot have:

any of the following:

dexlansoprazole (NLM:RXNORM:816346); or
esomeprazole (NLM:RXNORM:283742); or
lansoprazole (NLM:RXNORM:17128); or
pantoprazole (NLM:RXNORM:40790); or
Omeprazole (NLM:RXNORM:7646).

NASH and cirrhosis: The terms in this group occurred between Apr 1, 2003 and Jan 1, 2019

Patients must have:

all of the following:

Unspecified cirrhosis of liver (UMLS:ICD10CM:K74.60); and
Nonalcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH) (UMLS:ICD10CM:K75.81).

excluding Liver decompensation events: Any instance of excluding Liver decompensation events occurred on or before any instance of NASH and cirrhosis

Patients cannot have:

any of the following:

Spontaneous bacterial peritonitis (UMLS:ICD10CM:K65.2); or
Other sepsis (UMLS:ICD10CM:A41); or
Liver cell carcinoma (UMLS:ICD10CM:C22.0); or
Hepatic failure, not elsewhere classified (UMLS:ICD10CM:K72); or
Esophageal varices (UMLS:ICD10CM:I85); or
Hepatorenal syndrome (UMLS:ICD10CM:K76.7); or
Ascites (UMLS:ICD10CM:R18).

Appendix B – Text Representation of the Analysis Setup

This section contains the Index Event definition for each cohort.

The index event for Cohort 1 (query name: NASH PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23) is defined as the following:

All the following must be satisfied:

NASH and cirrhosis: The terms in this group occurred between Apr 1, 2003 and Jan 1, 2019

Patients must have:

all of the following:

Unspecified cirrhosis of liver (UMLS:ICD10CM:K74.60); and

Nonalcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH) (UMLS:ICD10CM:K75.81).

PPI: Any instance of PPI occurred within 3 months before or up to 3 years after any instance of NASH and cirrhosis

Patients must have:

any of the following:

dexlansoprazole (NLM:RXNORM:816346); or

esomeprazole (NLM:RXNORM:283742); or

lansoprazole (NLM:RXNORM:17128); or

pantoprazole (NLM:RXNORM:40790); or

Omeprazole (NLM:RXNORM:7646).

The index event for Cohort 2 (query name: NASH No PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23) is defined as the following:

All the following must be satisfied:

NASH and cirrhosis: The terms in this group occurred between Apr 1, 2003 and Jan 1, 2019

Patients must have:

all of the following:

Unspecified cirrhosis of liver (UMLS:ICD10CM:K74.60); and

Nonalcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH) (UMLS:ICD10CM:K75.81).

No PPI: Any instance of No PPI occurred within 3 months before or up to 3 years after any instance of NASH and cirrhosis

Patients cannot have:

any of the following:

dexlansoprazole (NLM:RXNORM:816346); or

esomeprazole (NLM:RXNORM:283742); or

lansoprazole (NLM:RXNORM:17128); or

pantoprazole (NLM:RXNORM:40790); or

Omeprazole (NLM:RXNORM:7646).

Appendix C – Text Representation of the Outcomes Definition

This analysis includes the following outcomes:

Ascites

Patients must have:

Ascites (UMLS:ICD10CM:R18).

Esophageal varices I85

Patients must have:

Esophageal varices (UMLS:ICD10CM:I85).

Esophageal varices w/o bleeding I85.0

Patients must have:

Esophageal varices without bleeding (UMLS:ICD10CM:I85.00).

Esophageal varices w/ bleeding I85.01

Patients must have:

Esophageal varices with bleeding (UMLS:ICD10CM:I85.01).

Hepatic failure, not elsewhere specified K72

Patients must have:

Hepatic failure, not elsewhere classified (UMLS:ICD10CM:K72).

Hepatic failure, unspecified K72.9

Patients must have:

Hepatic failure, unspecified (UMLS:ICD10CM:K72.9).

Hepatorenal syndrome K76.7

Patients must have:

Hepatorenal syndrome (UMLS:ICD10CM:K76.7).

Liver cell carcinoma C22.0

Patients must have:

Liver cell carcinoma (UMLS:ICD10CM:C22.0).

Sepsis A41

Patients must have:

Other sepsis (UMLS:ICD10CM:A41).

Sepsis Enterococcus A41.81

Patients must have:

Sepsis due to Enterococcus (UMLS:ICD10CM:A41.81).

Spontaneous bacterial peritonitis K65.2

Patients must have:

Spontaneous bacterial peritonitis (UMLS:ICD10CM:K65.2).

Mortality

Patients must have:
Deceased (Deceased).